

Optimization of the Preconditioner for the Jacobian-Split Newton-Krylov Method in Solving Neutronic and Thermal-Hydraulic Coupling Problem

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ABSTRACT

The neutronic and thermal-hydraulic (N/TH) coupling problem in high temperature gas-cooled reactor (HTGR) is important for nuclear reactor design and analysis. Newton-Krylov method is an advanced numerical method for solving large-scale nonlinear systems, which has been widely used to solve N-TH coupling problems. It featured with strong stability and super-linear convergence rate. Recently, an innovational Jacobian-Split Newton-Krylov (JSNK) method has been proposed. The core feature of this method is to split the original Jacobian matrix into two parts. The first part of Jacobian is explicitly constructed and serves as an efficient preconditioner for the Krylov subspace method. The second part of Jacobian is not formed. This work aims to find a more efficient preconditioner for JSNK method to further reduce the computational time. Three typical preconditioners are obtained by ignoring some terms from the Jacobian. A N/TH coupling model in HTGR was used to assess the performance of JSNK under different types of preconditioners. The results show that: It is profitable to construct a preconditioner for JSNK by removing some unimportant terms from Jacobian, which can reduce the matrix ILU factorization time. Even when employing the same sparsity pattern for the preconditioner, JSNK outperforms Jacobian-free Newton-Krylov (JFNK) in terms of both computational time and iteration count.

Keywords: Jacobian-Split Newton-Krylov; Preconditioner; Neutronic and Thermal-Hydraulic; HTGR.

1. INTRODUCTION

The nuclear reactor is a complex multi-physics coupling system, which involves neutronics, thermal-hydraulics, chemistry reactions, material deformation, and so on. These physical fields interact with each other, forming a complicated nonlinear system. It is a challenging issue to solve such a complicated nonlinear system in a stable and efficient way.

The Newton-Krylov method is an advanced numerical method for solving the large-scale nonlinear system. It is a combination of Newton's method for solving nonlinear equations and the Krylov subspace method for solving Newton's linearization equation. The coefficient matrix of Newton's linearization equation is known as the Jacobian matrix, whose elements are the partial derivative of each nonlinear equation to each unknown. Based on whether the Jacobian matrix is explicitly constructed, the Newton-Krylov method can be classified into Jacobian-Free Newton-Krylov (JFNK) method [1] and Finite Difference Jacobian-based Newton-Krylov (DJNK) method [2]. The JFNK method does not explicitly form the Jacobian matrix, but instead uses finite differencing to approximate the product of the Jacobian matrix with a vector. However, this approach requires additional effort to construct the preconditioning matrix. In contrast, the DJNK method explicitly constructs the Jacobian matrix and directly utilizes it as the preconditioning matrix.

Recently, an innovational Jacobian-Split Newton-Krylov (JSNK) method [3] has been proposed, which was originally designed for the Jacobian matrix with dense rows/blocks. The core feature of the JSNK method is to split the original Jacobian matrix into two parts (denoted by \mathbf{P} and \mathbf{R}). The first part \mathbf{P} is

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explicitly constructed using finite differences and graph coloring algorithm and serves as an efficient preconditioner for the Krylov subspace iteration method. The remaining part \mathbf{R} is not explicitly formed and employs a “Jacobian-free” strategy. Compared with JFNK, JSNK costs fewer Krylov iterations due to owning a better preconditioner. Compared with DJNK, JSNK costs less Jacobian computational time when there is a dense row/block in Jacobian matrix. Besides, JSNK can also achieve a super-linear convergence like JFNK and DJNK.

Although the JSNK was originally designed for the Jacobian matrix with dense rows/blocks, we find that it can also be used to construct various preconditioners by splitting some derivative terms into the remaining part \mathbf{R} . Different non-zero patterns in the preconditioner will affect the preconditioning time and Krylov iterations. There is a trade-off between the completeness of the preconditioner and its computational cost: retaining more non-zero elements reduces Krylov iterations at the expense of increased preconditioning time. In this work, to further reduce the JSNK’s computational time, several preconditioners (obtained by splitting the Jacobian) are proposed and compared. A neutronics/thermal-hydraulics nonlinear coupling problem arising from the simplified high-temperature gas-coolant reactor is utilized to assess the performance of JSNK with different preconditioners.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. A neutronics/thermal-hydraulics coupling model of HTGR is described in **Section 2**. The numerical methods are briefly introduced in **Section 3**, including JFNK method, JSNK method, and their preconditioners. The numerical results are given in **Section 4**, in which the three different preconditioners are compared. The discussion and conclusion are presented in **Section 5**.

2. PHYSICAL MODEL

A simplified homogeneous high-temperature gas-coolant reactor (HTGR) model in cylindrical coordinates is used in this work. The governing equations are shown below:

(a) Steady-state multigroup neutronic diffusion equation:

$$F\phi_g = \nabla \cdot D_g \bar{\nabla} \phi_g - \Sigma_{r,g} \phi_g + \sum_{g'=1(g' \neq g)}^G (\Sigma_{s,g' \rightarrow g} \phi_{g'}) + \frac{\chi_g}{k} \sum_{g'=1}^G (v \Sigma_{f,g'} \phi_{g'}) = 0 \quad (1)$$

Where g and g' are the group indexes; k is the multiplication factor. ν is the average number of neutrons emitted per fission. The terms ϕ_g , D_g , $\Sigma_{r,g}$, $\Sigma_{s,g' \rightarrow g}$, $\Sigma_{f,g}$, χ_g are the neutron scalar flux, diffusion coefficient, removal macro cross-section, scattering macro cross-section, fission macro cross-section, and fission spectrum of g -th group, respectively.

(b) Steady-state fuel temperature conservation equation:

$$F_{T_s} = \nabla \cdot \lambda_s \bar{\nabla} T_s + (1 - \varepsilon) \frac{E_{\text{eff}}}{k} \sum_{g=1}^G (\Sigma_{f,g} \phi_g) + \alpha A (T_c - T_s) = 0 \quad (2)$$

Where, T_s is the solid fuel temperature; T_c is the coolant temperature; λ_s is the heat conductivity of solid fuel; α is the heat transfer coefficient; A is the heat transfer area per unit volume; ε is the porosity of the reactor core; E_{eff} is the energy release per fission.

(c) Steady-state coolant temperature conservation equation:

$$F_{T_c} = \nabla \cdot \lambda_c \bar{\nabla} T_c + \alpha A (T_s - T_c) - \varepsilon \rho_c c_{pc} (\bar{\mathbf{U}} \cdot \bar{\nabla} T_c) = 0 \quad (3)$$

Where the terms ρ_c , λ_c , c_{pc} are coolant density, coolant heat conductivity, and coolant heat capacity; $\bar{\mathbf{U}}$ is the coolant velocity vector, which consists of velocities in radial (U), axial (V), and azimuthal (W).

(d) Steady-state coolant pressure conservation equation (Poisson equation):

$$F_{P_c} = \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\frac{\rho_c}{K} r \frac{\partial P_c}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left[\frac{\rho_c}{K} \left(\frac{\partial P_c}{\partial z} - \rho_c g \right) \right] + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \left(\frac{\rho_c}{K} \frac{\partial P_c}{\partial \theta} \right) = 0 \quad (4)$$

Where, P_c is the coolant pressure; K is the coolant resistance coefficient; g is the gravitational acceleration; r, z, θ are the radius, height, and azimuth angle, respectively.

(e) **Steady-state Coolant velocity conservation equation:**

$$F_U = -\frac{\partial P_c}{\partial r} - K \cdot U = 0 \quad (5)$$

$$F_V = -\frac{\partial P_c}{\partial z} + \rho_c g - K \cdot V = 0 \quad (6)$$

$$F_W = -\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial P_c}{\partial \theta} - K \cdot W = 0 \quad (7)$$

(f) **Governing equation for multiplication factor k in steady state:**

The constraint equation should be added for the multiplication factor k because it is treated as an unknown parameter. Here, the thermal power constraint equation is considered:

$$F_k = \iiint (1 - \varepsilon) \frac{E_{\text{eff}}}{k} \sum_{g=1}^G (\Sigma_{f,g} \phi_g) dV - P_{\text{th}} = 0 \quad (8)$$

P_{th} is the thermal power of the reactor in the steady state. The neutron reaction cross-section is dependent on the solid fuel temperature. The density, heat conductivity, and heat capacity are also nonlinear functions of temperature. The heat transfer coefficient α depends on the coolant pressure and the coolant velocity. In summary, the nonlinear function derived from this coupling problem consists of Eq. (1), (2), (3), (4), (5), (6), (7), and (8). The unknowns include: four-group neutron flux ϕ_g , the solid fuel temperature T_s , the coolant temperature T_c , the coolant pressure P_c , the coolant velocity in radial (U), axial (V), azimuthal (W), and the multiplication factor k . The nonlinear function $\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x})$ and unknowns \mathbf{x} are shown in Eq. (9).

$$\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}) = [F_{\phi_g}, F_{T_s}, F_{T_c}, F_{P_c}, F_{\vec{U}}, F_k]^T, \text{ where } \mathbf{x} = [\phi_g, T_s, T_c, P_c, \vec{U}, k]^T \quad (9)$$

The corresponding Jacobian matrix of the nonlinear function $\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x})$ is given in Eq. (10). In which, the derivative term J_{ϕ_g, T_s} is defined as $J_{\phi_g, T_s} \triangleq \partial F_{\phi_g} / \partial T_s$. Other derivative terms are defined similarly. Note that, in the last row, the residual F_k is the function of neutron flux and temperature at all points due to the integral of the fission rate over space. Therefore, there are many non-zeroes in the term J_{k, ϕ_g} and J_{k, T_s} , i.e., the last row is a dense row. This dense row will not be formed explicitly through the Jacobian splitting strategy.

$$J(\mathbf{x}) \triangleq \frac{\partial \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x})}{\partial \mathbf{x}} = \begin{bmatrix} J_{\phi_g, \phi_g} & J_{\phi_g, T_s} & & & & J_{\phi_g, k} \\ J_{T_s, \phi_g} & J_{T_s, T_s} & J_{T_s, T_c} & J_{T_s, P_c} & J_{T_s, U} & J_{T_s, k} \\ & J_{T_c, T_s} & J_{T_c, T_c} & J_{T_c, P_c} & J_{T_c, U} & \\ & & J_{P_c, T_c} & J_{P_c, P_c} & J_{P_c, U} & \\ & & J_{U, T_c} & J_{U, P_c} & J_{U, U} & \\ J_{k, \phi_g} & J_{k, T_s} & & & & J_{k, k} \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

3. METHOD

3.1. Newton-Krylov Method

The Newton-Krylov (NK) method is a widely used numerical method to solve the large-scale nonlinear equations $\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{0}$, where $\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x})$ is a vector-valued function of nonlinear residuals and $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the solution vector to be found. At each Newton iteration, Newton's linearization equation (Eq. (11)) is solved by the Krylov subspace method iteratively. In which, the coefficient matrix $\mathbf{J}(\mathbf{x})$ is called the Jacobian matrix, whose elements are the first derivatives of nonlinear function $\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x})$. \mathbf{P} is the

Where, the term $F_P(\mathbf{x})$ and $F_R(\mathbf{x})$ are the residual functions of two parts. The term $J_P(\mathbf{x})$ and $J_R(\mathbf{x})$ are two derivative matrices corresponding to $F_P(\mathbf{x})$ and $F_R(\mathbf{x})$. The sparse part $J_P(\mathbf{x})$ is explicitly constructed by finite differences and graph coloring algorithm [8], [9], and used as a preconditioner in the Krylov subspace method. The remaining part $J_R(\mathbf{x})$ is not explicitly constructed. When performing matrix-vector product, it is approximated by finite difference. Therefore, in each GMRES iteration, the Jacobian-vector product can be evaluated as Eq. (17),

$$J(\mathbf{x}) \cdot \mathbf{v} = J_P(\mathbf{x}) \cdot \mathbf{v} + J_R(\mathbf{x}) \cdot \mathbf{v} \approx J_P(\mathbf{x}) \cdot \mathbf{v} + \frac{F_R(\mathbf{x} + \epsilon \mathbf{v}) - F_R(\mathbf{x})}{\epsilon} \quad (17)$$

The main difference between JSNK and JFNK lies in the Jacobian-vector product and the preconditioner. JFNK performs Jacobian-vector following Eq. (12), while the JSNK uses Eq. (17). Besides, no available matrix can be used as a preconditioner directly in JFNK. While the JSNK can use $\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{x})$ as preconditioner directly.

3.2. Preconditioner Strategies for the JSNK Method

By explicitly constructing the sparse part $J_P(\mathbf{x})$ of the Jacobian matrix, the JSNK method can utilize this matrix as an efficient preconditioner. Different splitting patterns will lead to the preconditioners with different non-zero patterns. This work considers the following three typical preconditioners for the JSNK method, shown in Eq. (18) ~ Eq. (20).

Preconditioner 1: Only splitting the dense row from the original Jacobian matrix, i.e., the terms J_{k,ϕ_g} and J_{k,T_s} in the last row. The dense row must be split because it will cause a huge computational burden in matrix evaluation and ILU factorization.

$$\mathbf{P}_1 = \begin{bmatrix} J_{\phi_g,\phi_g} & J_{\phi_g,T_s} & & & & J_{\phi_g,k} \\ J_{T_s,\phi_g} & J_{T_s,T_s} & J_{T_s,T_c} & J_{T_s,P_c} & J_{T_s,U} & J_{T_s,k} \\ & J_{T_c,T_s} & J_{T_c,T_c} & J_{T_c,P_c} & J_{T_c,U} & \\ & & J_{P_c,T_c} & J_{P_c,P_c} & J_{P_c,U} & \\ & & J_{U,T_c} & J_{U,P_c} & J_{U,U} & \\ 0 & 0 & & & & J_{k,k} \end{bmatrix} \quad (18)$$

Preconditioner 2: Based on preconditioner 1, split the specified Jacobian terms $J_{T_s,P_c}, J_{T_s,U}$. These terms were introduced by heat transfer coefficient α in Eq. (2).

$$\mathbf{P}_2 = \begin{bmatrix} J_{\phi_g,\phi_g} & J_{\phi_g,T_s} & & & & J_{\phi_g,k} \\ J_{T_s,\phi_g} & J_{T_s,T_s} & J_{T_s,T_c} & 0 & 0 & J_{T_s,k} \\ & J_{T_c,T_s} & J_{T_c,T_c} & J_{T_c,P_c} & J_{T_c,U} & \\ & & J_{P_c,T_c} & J_{P_c,P_c} & J_{P_c,U} & \\ & & J_{U,T_c} & J_{U,P_c} & J_{U,U} & \\ 0 & 0 & & & & J_{k,k} \end{bmatrix} \quad (19)$$

Preconditioner 3: Using the same non-zero pattern as JFNK's preconditioner defined in Eq. (13).

$$\mathbf{P}_3 = \begin{bmatrix} J_{\phi_g,\phi_g} & 0 & & & & 0 \\ J_{T_s,\phi_g} & J_{T_s,T_s} & J_{T_s,T_c} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & J_{T_c,T_s} & J_{T_c,T_c} & 0 & 0 & \\ & & 0 & J_{P_c,P_c} & 0 & \\ & & 0 & J_{U,P_c} & J_{U,U} & \\ 0 & 0 & & & & J_{k,k} \end{bmatrix} \quad (20)$$

In terms of the number of non-zeros in three preconditioners: $P_1 > P_2 > P_3$. The first preconditioner P_1 has the most Jacobian elements. The preconditioner P_2 is a more economical preconditioner. The preconditioner P_3 is designed to compare with JFNK's physics-based preconditioner under the same non-zero pattern. Note that it only needs to provide the non-zero pattern of the Jacobian for JSNK. The element value in the Jacobian is calculated automatically by the finite difference method.

4. NUMERICAL EXPERIMENTS

In this section, the computational performance of the JSNK method is evaluated by solving the simplified 3-D homogeneous HTGR reactor model described in Section 2. There are 16 meshes in radial direction, 35 meshes in axial direction, and 30 meshes in azimuthal direction. The total number of unknowns is 102001. The dimension of the Jacobian matrix is 102001×102001 .

The Krylov subspace iteration method chooses the right preconditioned Generalized Minimal RESidual (GMRES) method. The maximum Krylov subspace dimension and the maximum number of iterations for GMRES are 100 and 300, respectively, without restarting. The linear convergence criterion for GMRES is set as $\|r_m\| < 10^{-6}\|r_0\|$ and the nonlinear convergence criterion for Newton iteration is set as $\|F(x_k)\| < 10^{-10}\|F(x_0)\|$. The incomplete lower-upper factorization with different fill-in levels (ILU(k)) is employed to approximate the inverse of the preconditioner matrix. The Reverse Cuthill-McKee ordering [10] is utilized to reduce the fill-in during ILU factorization.

JSNK is tested under three different preconditioners. They are denoted by JSNK-P1, JSNK-P2, and JSNK-P3, respectively. The number of non-zeros in the three preconditioners is 1800601, 1318021, and 925981, respectively. JFNK with a physical-based preconditioner is used to compare with JSNK. The physical-based preconditioner has 925981 non-zeros. The number of fill-ins after ILU factorization is given in the following test, which is normalized by the number of non-zeros in JFNK's preconditioner. Take JSNK-P1 as an example, the normalized number of fill-ins in ILU(0) is $1800601/925981 = 1.94$.

Figure 1 shows the GMRES iterations, the normalized number of fill-ins, and the total time under different ILU fill-in levels.

Figure 1(a) shows the number of GMRES iterations under different fill-in levels. JSNK-P1 uses the fewest iterations, followed by JSNK-P2, JSNK-P3, and JFNK. The GMRES iterations of JSNK-P1 and JSNK-P2 are almost the same, which means that the simplification of the preconditioner in JSNK-P2 is feasible. JSNK with three preconditioners all cost fewer GMRES iterations than JFNK. Moreover, JSNK-P3 uses fewer iterations than JFNK, although their preconditioners share the same non-zero structure. The reason is that JFNK's preconditioner is just an approximation of the Jacobian. Some additional derivative terms are ignored in JFNK's preconditioner.

Figure 1(b) shows the number of fill-ins under different fill-in levels. The vertical axis represents the fill-in ratio compared with ILU(0). The number of fill-ins of JSNK and JFNK increases with the fill-in level, following a quadratic growth rate. JFNK and JSNK-P3 use fewer fill-ins, followed by JSNK-P2 and JSNK-P1.

Figure 1(c) shows the total computational time under different fill-in levels. With the increase of fill-in level, the total computational time increases first and then decreases. In which JSNK-P2 preconditioned with ILU(3) costs the least time.

Figure 1(d) shows the detailed time composition of JSNK and JFNK under the ILU(3). For JSNK method, it costs about 50% time on Jacobian computing. But it costs less time in the Jacobian-vector product because the explicit Jacobian-vector product is more efficient. Besides, JSNK costs less time in orthogonalization because it requires fewer GMRES iterations. While JFNK costs about 80% time in the Jacobian-vector product and GMRES orthogonalization, because it requires more GMRES iterations.

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(a) GMRES Iterations

(b) Normalized Number of Fill-ins

(c) Total Time

(d) Detailed Time Consumption under the ILU(3)

Figure 1. Evaluation of JSNK Preconditioners: GMRES Iterations, ILU Fill-ins, and Time Cost.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The Jacobian-Split Newton-Krylov method is a promising numerical method for solving complex nonlinear equations. This method splits the original Jacobian matrix into two parts. The first part can serve as an efficient preconditioner for the Krylov subspace method. Different split patterns can generate various preconditioners according to user needs, which is very flexible. In this work, the JSNK preconditioned with three typical preconditioners is tested. Several conclusions could be made:

- (1) The removal of unimportant terms from the Jacobian offers an effective means of constructing a JSNK preconditioner, which in turn decreases ILU fill-ins and computational cost without significantly increasing the number of GMRES iterations.
- (2) In terms of total calculation time, the best preconditioner for JSNK is the preconditioner P_2 , which split the dense row (J_{k,ϕ_g} and J_{k,T_s}) and some solid temperature derivative terms (J_{T_s,P_c} , $J_{T_s,U}$) from the Jacobian matrix.
- (3) Even when employing the same nonzero pattern as the JFNK preconditioner, the JSNK method maintains an advantage due to its more accurate preconditioner matrix entries.

In conclusion, JSNK is a very efficient and flexible numerical method for solving complicated coupling problems. In the future, the JSNK will be applied to solve more complex coupling problems, such as two-phase flow in a steam generator and simultaneous solution of reactor core and steam generator.

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